

Primary Studies

Study ID	Title	Type	Year
S01	An Architecture to Automate Performance Tests on Microservices	Conference	2016
S02	A Full Stack Microservices Framework with Business Modelling	Conference	2018
S03	A microservice development for document management system	Conference	2017
S04	A microservices architecture for collaborative document editing enhanced with face recognition	Conference	2016
S05	A Reusable Automated Acceptance Testing Architecture for Microservices in Behavior-Driven Development	Conference	2015
S06	A Service Framework for Parallel Test Execution on a Developer's Local Development Workstation	Conference	2015
S07	Automation of regression test in microservice architecture	Conference	2018
S08	CIDE: An Integrated Development Environment for Microservices	Conference	2016
S09	EvoMaster: Evolutionary Multi-context Automated System Test Generation	Workshop	2019
S10	Gremlin: Systematic Resilience Testing of Microservices	Conference	2016
S11	Microservices: Architecting for Continuous Delivery and DevOps	Workshop	2018
S12	Run-Time Reliability Estimation of Microservice Architectures	Conference	2018
S13	Towards Executable Specifications for Microservices	Conference	2018
S14	Using Service Dependency Graph to Analyze and Test Microservices	Conference	2018
S15	A Formal Framework for Specifying and Verifying Microservices Based Process Flows	Conference	2017
S16	Automation and intelligent scheduling of distributed system functional testing	Journal	2017
S17	Microservice-Based Agile Architectures: An Opportunity for Specialized Niche Technologies	Conference	2018
S18	Microservices tenets	Journal	2017
S19	Joint testing and profiling of microservice-based network services using TTCN-3	Conference	2018

S20	Learning-Based Testing of Distributed Microservice Architectures: Correctness and Fault Injection	Workshop	2015
S21	Microservices validation: Mjolnirr platform case study	Conference	2015
S22	Comparison of Runtime Testing Tools for Microservices	Conference	2019
S23	Microservice Architectures for Advanced Driver Assistance Systems: A Case-Study	Conference	2019
S24	Performance and Scalability Testing Strategy Based on Kubemark	Conference	2019
S25	Applying Change Impact Analysis Test to Migration Test Case Extraction Based on IDAU and Graph Analysis Techniques	Conference	2019
S26	Continuous Integration of Applications for ONOS	Conference	2019
S27	Microservice-Tailored Generation of Session-Based Workload Models for Representative Load Testing	Conference	2019
S28	On Monolithic and Microservice Deployment of Network Functions	Conference	2019
S29	Consumer-Driven Contract Tests for Microservices: A Case Study	Conference	2019
S30	A Continuous Delivery Pipeline for EA Model Evolution	Conference	2019
S31	Graph-based and scenario-driven microservice analysis, retrieval, and testing	Journal	2019

Conference	24
Journal	4
Workshop	3
Total	31

2015	4
2016	4
2017	4
2018	8
2019	11
Total	31